

Evaluating LSTM-Based Acoustic-to-Articulatory Inversion with Ultrasound Tongue Imaging

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Abstract. Speech and language therapy (SLT) for individuals with speech sound disorders (SSDs) requires tools that can make articulatory movements, particularly tongue motion, more visible and interpretable. Ultrasound tongue imaging (UTI) is a promising modality for this purpose, as it is non-invasive, safe, and does not interfere with natural speech. In this work, we investigate the use of recurrent neural networks for acoustic-to-articulatory inversion (AAI), directly mapping speech audio features to corresponding UTI frames. We implement a deep LSTM architecture and evaluate its performance under different loss functions. Our experiments compare pixel-based losses (MSE, MAE), perceptual losses (SSIM), and hybrid combinations. While the models failed to generalize effectively to the unseen data, we observed that the choice of loss function significantly influenced perceptual frame quality. MSE loss emphasized sharper pixel contrast but missed structural accuracy, whereas SSIM improved structure at the cost of sharpness. Hybrid losses, particularly SSIM+MAE with weighting, produced the most visually convincing reconstructions, despite modest quantitative metrics. These findings demonstrate both the limitations of LSTM-based AAI for UTI generation and the importance of carefully designed loss functions. They suggest that future work should integrate hybrid loss formulations with alternative architectures to achieve more reliable mappings from speech to tongue imaging.

Keywords: Speech and language therapy · Ultrasound tongue imaging · Acoustic to articulatory inversion · Deep learning

1 Introduction

Speech Sound Disorders (SSDs) affect a substantial proportion of the population, undermining the effectiveness of speech as the primary mode of communication and hindering intelligibility in everyday interaction [23]. Early diagnosis and treatment can improve outcomes [14], but access to Speech Language Therapy (SLT) remains limited due to therapist shortages, long waiting times, and the demands of individualized care [3]. Although SLT is effective, sustaining engagement and providing timely, tailored feedback continue to pose significant challenges in traditional practice.

In recent years, digital technologies have emerged as promising tools to support SLT. Computer applications, mobile platforms, and interactive systems combined with Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques provide scalable ways to support assessment and intervention. Automatic speech recognition (ASR) and signal processing methods allow the transcription and analysis of speech, enabling impairment detection, real-time feedback, and progress tracking. These approaches show potential in reducing reliance on in-person therapy and extending access to effective intervention [9].

One of the key challenges in SLT, however, lies in visualizing articulatory movements, particularly tongue motion. Traditional therapy often involves the clinician illustrating tongue placement on diagrams or demonstrating expected motion patterns [16]. Current techniques for capturing tongue movements include magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), electropalatography (EPG), and Ultrasound Tongue Imaging (UTI). Among these, UTI has significant advantages: it is non-invasive, safe, and does not interfere with natural speech production, making it well-suited for both research and clinical use [4]. UTI produces two-dimensional grayscale images that represent tongue surface motion, capturing articulatory dynamics in real time.

Building on this, researchers have explored Audio to Articulatory Inversion (AAI), a field concerned with predicting articulatory configurations directly from acoustic speech signals. AAI offers the possibility of bypassing expensive imaging equipment by training models that map audio features to ultrasound frames, enabling scalable and low-cost visualization of articulatory dynamics. Several models have been proposed for AAI, ranging from simple recurrent architectures to more complex generative designs. LSTMs, in particular, are a natural candidate due to their ability to model temporal dependencies in sequential data [15].

In this work, we address the challenge of evaluating AAI models for mapping speech to ultrasound. While AAI is recognized as an important yet difficult task, a central question remains: Which evaluation metrics best capture performance in this task? Specifically, we investigate whether pixel-based losses (Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE)), perceptual losses (Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM)), or hybrid formulations provide a more reliable indicator of model success. The model is derived from a prior work exploring baseline LSTM architectures for AAI and serves as a starting point for analyzing the strengths and limitations of recurrent approaches in this multi-modal mapping task [20]. Our experiments highlight the critical role of loss function design in shaping perceptual UTI frame quality and provide insights into future directions for improving speech-to-ultrasound generation. Besides that, this work represents an attempt to support individuals with SSDs by providing accessible and low-cost therapeutic tools, while also assisting speech-language therapists by reducing workload and enabling more personalized, effective diagnostic and treatment planning.

2 Background and Related Work

Research on AAI and articulatory modeling has explored a wide range of modalities and neural architectures, with UTI emerging as a promising non-invasive technique. Early work extended DNN-based text-to-speech frameworks to incorporate articulatory prediction, demonstrating that deep neural networks can generate synchronized tongue motion using Principal Component Analysis (PCA)-compressed ultrasound images [6]. This study highlighted the feasibility of text-to-articulatory mapping and its potential applications in pronunciation training and audiovisual synthesis, though performance was limited by small datasets and loss of fine structural detail in the generated outputs.

Subsequent research investigated UTI regeneration methods to address variability in probe alignment and missing data [13]. By comparing one-step and two-step reconstruction processes, the study showed that high SSIM scores do not always guarantee faithful articulatory detail, underscoring the need for refined regeneration techniques. Parallel to this, brain-computer interface (BCI) approaches integrated Electroencephalography (EEG) signals with UTI for articulatory decoding [8]. While these methods demonstrated a weak but noticeable link between EEG and tongue imaging, mel-spectrogram-based AAI consistently produced more accurate predictions, confirming the limitations of EEG-based models for fine-grained articulation.

In terms of direct acoustic-to-articulatory mapping, fully connected DNNs have been used to predict UTI frames from spectral features [17]. Experiments indicated that relatively simple architectures with limited depth often outperform more complex models when training data is scarce. Moreover, SSIM and its variants were identified as a more perceptually reliable evaluation metric than traditional pixel-based measures. Extending this framework beyond ultrasound, real-time MRI (rtMRI) has also been explored as an articulatory target for inversion [5]. Studies comparing CNN, DNN, and LSTM models demonstrated that recurrent architectures are most effective for capturing temporal dependencies, with LSTMs achieving the lowest normalized MSE and highest SSIM scores. However, rtMRI suffers from low frame rates, noise artifacts, and higher expertise and acquisition costs, making ultrasound comparatively more attractive for scalable clinical applications.

Overall, these works establish the promise of deep learning methods for articulatory modeling while also exposing recurring challenges: limited dataset sizes, inter-speaker variability, loss of fine-grained structural detail, and difficulties in generalizing across modalities. Within this context, LSTM-based AAI remains a baseline approach, offering temporal modeling but struggling with generalization in small-data scenarios. Motivated by this background, we focus on an LSTM-based AAI model, systematically evaluating its performance under different loss functions to better understand the strengths and limitations of recurrent approaches for speech-to-ultrasound generation.

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset and Preprocessing

The dataset we utilized is the UltraSuite TaL1 corpus [10, 19], a single-speaker audio–ultrasound dataset recorded across multiple days. Each utterance includes synchronized mid-sagittal UTI and speech audio, accompanied by ultrasound parameter files (providing, e.g., `FramesPerSec` and `TimeInSecsOfFirstFrame` for synchronization). Following the project codebase, we exclude day1 files that lack reliable video sync and use day2–day6. TaL1 contains 1246 read-utterance files, corresponding to 1.16 hours of read speech in total. After removing the 206 unsynchronized day1 items, 1039 files remain available for experiments.

In the preprocessing step, UTI sequences were temporally resampled to 60 fps and spatially resized to 64×128 pixels following the guidelines of Speech2Ult repository [20]. Frames were grayscale-normalized to $[0,1]$ using `MinMax` scaling (fit on training, applied to validation/test) and synchronized with audio via the `TimeInSecsOfFirstFrame` parameter, after which all modalities were trimmed to the minimum common duration. Silence was removed consistently from both audio and ultrasound streams using voice-activity detection (VAD) from the UltraSuite tools [10]. For models requiring vectorized data (e.g., DNNs, LSTMs), frames were flattened to 8192-dimensional vectors. For the speech part, the audio file was loaded at 20 kHz, and 20 Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) were computed with a hop length matched to the ultrasound frame period and a 20 ms analysis window. Delta features of the MFCCs were concatenated, yielding 40 features per frame. Audio features were standardized using z-score statistics from the training split and applied to validation and test. We perform a randomized 80/10/10 split (train/validation/test) over utterance files with a fixed seed to ensure reproducibility. The preprocessing pipeline stores the file-level boundaries so that reshaping for sequence models (LSTM) preserves utterance integrity and avoids leakage across splits. For the LSTM network, we construct audio sequences with a lookback of 10 frames.

3.2 Model Architecture

In this work, we implemented an LSTM model based on the Speech2Ult repository [20], as such architectures are widely used in speech processing due to their ability to capture temporal dependencies across sequences.

The LSTM architecture was designed with several regularization techniques to mitigate overfitting while capturing temporal dynamics. Each input sequence of acoustic features was first processed by three time-distributed dense layers with 575 hidden units—following the validated architecture used in Speech2MRI [5]—and ReLU activation, ensuring consistent frame-level feature extraction across time [21]. Batch normalization, dropout (0.3), and L2 regularization were applied to stabilize training and improve generalization. These layers followed by two stacked LSTM layers with 575 units each: the first returned full sequences to capture temporal dependencies, while the second returned the final hidden

state to summarize articulatory dynamics across frames. Finally, this representation was mapped through a linear dense layer to reconstruct UTI frames of size 64×128 pixels [7]. Figure 1 illustrates the model architecture.

Fig. 1: LSTM model architecture for audio (input) to ultrasound (output) mapping, inspired by the Speech2Ult framework[20].

4 Experiments

All experiments were executed on a university high-performance computing cluster managed by SLURM. Jobs were scheduled on a GPU node within a large GPU partition, with 32 GB system memory and 4 CPU cores allocated per task. Models were implemented in TensorFlow/Keras and executed within an isolated Conda environment.

For the experiments models were trained with the Adam optimizer using a batch size of 128 for 50 epochs and early stopping. All experiments use the pre-processed single-speaker TaL1 dataset, aligned at the frame level. The input consists of 40-dimensional audio features (20 MFCCs plus 20 delta coefficients) with a lookback window of 10 frames to provide temporal context. We systematically compared several loss functions to investigate their influence on reconstruction quality. Pixel-based losses included MSE and MAE. Perceptual losses included the SSIM, applied in the form $1 - \text{SSIM}$ on normalized frames. Hybrid formulations combined pixel and perceptual terms, including SSIM+MAE, SSIM+MSE, and MS-SSIM + MAE. These objectives were selected based on prior work in medical image generation, with the goal of balancing sharpness and structural

fidelity [26]. We report MSE and MAE as pixel-level metrics, and SSIM as a perceptual metric, computed on $[0,1]$ normalized grayscale frames at 64×128 resolution. In addition to quantitative evaluation, qualitative comparisons were conducted by visual observation of predicted frames and short reconstructed sequences to assess temporal stability. All preprocessing steps (normalization and dataset splits) were fixed across runs to ensure comparability.

5 Results

To evaluate, we implemented recurrent baselines trained on the TaL1 dataset. Table 1 reports the performance across experiments in terms of the composite loss, MAE, MSE, and SIM.

Table 1: LSTM Speech2UIt results under different loss configurations.

Loss function	Loss ↓	MAE ↓	MSE ↓	SSIM ↑
MAE	0.092	0.092	0.020	0.174
MSE	0.019	0.095	0.019	0.143
SSIM	0.832	0.147	0.081	0.168
SSIM + MSE	0.706	0.110	0.030	0.176
SSIM + MAE	0.711	0.104	0.027	0.187

Figure 2 shows the training and validation loss curves for the best-performing loss function that achieved the highest SSIM score. The results indicate that the model fails to generalize the learned representations to the validation set.

Fig. 2: Training and validation loss curves for the best-performing loss function based on the SSIM score. The divergence highlights the model’s limited ability to generalize to unseen validation data.

Another important observation is the perceptual effect of different loss functions on the generated frames, beyond the quantitative metrics reported in Table 1. Figure 3 illustrates ultrasound frames generated under different loss functions, shown alongside the ground truth frame for comparison.

Fig. 3: Comparison of generated ultrasound frames obtained using identical architecture and training settings but optimized with different loss functions.

6 Discussion

An important observation from our experiments is the influence of loss function choice. While MAE, MSE, and SSIM are the most common image similarity metrics in AAI and medical imaging, they produced only modest differences in numerical performance. However, perceptual inspection revealed that the generated frames varied considerably in appearance depending on the chosen loss. As shown in Figure 3, the reconstructed frames appear perceptually plausible despite the modest metric scores. Models trained with MSE and MAE produced outputs that were blurry but sharper in contrast, better capturing pixel intensity variations, though often lacking structural accuracy. In contrast, SSIM-based models yielded outputs with improved structural fidelity and reduced blurriness, but at the cost of sharpness and contrast. To combine these benefits, a hybrid SSIM+MAE loss was adopted, which produced reconstructions that were both structurally more coherent and visually sharper, outperforming individual SSIM or MSE losses in qualitative evaluation. This observation aligns with findings in the literature, which suggest that weighted hybrid losses better balance contrast and structural fidelity [26]. In particular, the formulation

$$\mathcal{L} = \alpha \cdot (1 - \text{SSIM}) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \text{L1},$$

with $\alpha = 0.84$, has been reported as effective for image reconstruction tasks. In our experiments, the SSIM+MAE loss indeed produced the most perceptually

convincing frames, even though the numerical SSIM values remained modest (0.187 at best). Other evaluation metrics, such as Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) [12], Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) [11], Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS) [25], and Complex-Wavelet SSIM (CW-SSIM) [22], are occasionally used in the literature. However, these require either large datasets (FID, LPIPS) to produce stable and meaningful evaluations, limiting their applicability in data-scarce domains [11, 25] or are more suitable when results are already reliable enough to merit fine-grained comparison. Based on this, for this initial experiment, we restricted evaluation to the most widely used metrics to maintain comparability with prior studies.

In this study, we evaluated an LSTM-based AAI model, building upon the Speech2Utl repository originally proposed in a master’s thesis at the University of Edinburgh [20]. While we introduced modifications, the central idea remained to map audio features (MFCCs and their deltas, forming 40-dimensional input vectors) to UTI at a resolution of 64×128 pixels. This corresponds to a high-dimensional output space of 8192 values per frame, making the mapping problem highly challenging and data-intensive. As an initial experiment, we selected this architecture because LSTMs are among the most frequently proposed baselines in the literature, allowing for a meaningful comparison with existing work. Although the predicted frames showed some structural plausibility at the visual level, the quantitative metrics reflected limited performance, underscoring the difficulty of the task. Numerous configurations and regularization strategies were tested, but none produced a substantial improvement in generalization. Despite the strategies used to prevent overfitting, the models consistently exhibited poor generalization. Training loss curves decreased steadily, but validation losses remained flat, indicating that the models were unable to learn meaningful mappings from audio to ultrasound that generalized beyond the training set.

One of the key factors limiting AAI performance is the quality of the acoustic features fed into the model; traditional hand-crafted representations such as MFCCs or filterbanks provide only a coarse summary of the signal and may fail to capture articulatory-relevant information. In contrast, recent self-supervised and pre-trained speech encoders such as wav2vec 2.0 [1] and Whisper [18], offer compact, high-level embeddings that carry rich phonetic, prosodic, and temporal structure learned from large-scale speech corpora. Incorporating such pre-trained representations in AAI could substantially reduce the burden on the model to learn low-level acoustic patterns from scratch, mitigate the effects of data scarcity, and provide a more informative intermediate space for mapping to ultrasound articulatory frames. Given the high dimensionality of UTI data and the inherent difficulty of the AAI task, exploring these speech encoders is a promising avenue for improving performance and simplifying the overall modeling pipeline.

The field of AAI remains relatively new, with limited experimental focus and a lack of standardized benchmarks. As a multimodal learning problem, AAI is inherently complex, requiring the mapping of data across different modalities. Despite the availability of some corpora containing paired audio and articulatory

data, dataset scarcity continues to be a key barrier, limiting model generalization and the development of reliable baselines. At present, although several strong approaches have been proposed for AAI, there is still no widely accepted benchmark model against which new methods can be consistently compared.

From a clinical perspective, the long-term motivation lies in supporting speech and language therapy. Visualizing tongue articulation is a critical component of clinical intervention [16], yet direct ultrasound imaging is resource-intensive and not always accessible. AAI methods, if further developed, could provide low-cost and scalable ways to approximate articulatory movements from speech recordings alone. Such technology could enable remote therapy, personalized feedback, and enhanced training materials where direct imaging is unavailable. While our results demonstrate the limitations of simple LSTM-based approaches, they also highlight the importance of continued research toward robust models that could eventually augment existing therapy practices and expand access to articulatory feedback tools. These methods must be developed in close collaboration with SLTs, incorporating their evaluation and feedback throughout the process. Such involvement is essential to ensure that the models address real clinical challenges and ultimately support practical, therapist-oriented problem solving in real-world settings.

7 Future Work

These findings highlight both the promise and limitations of recurrent models in AAI. Future work should address three main challenges. First, the high dimensional mismatch between audio features and UTI frames makes direct prediction difficult; compact embeddings may offer a better intermediate space. Second, diffusion models offer particular advantages for multimodal learning, as their integration of attention mechanisms allows them to focus on different parts of a sequence in a structured and context-aware manner [2]. A recent work on audio-textual diffusion models [24] demonstrates the potential of this direction for cross-modal generation. Third, progress will require larger datasets and robust benchmarks, alongside richer evaluation protocols that go beyond pixel similarity to capture perceptual and clinical utility. Finally, additional evaluation metrics should be introduced to better capture perceptual differences in generated frames, enabling more systematic and meaningful comparisons. Advancing along these lines can establish AAI as a reliable tool for bridging acoustic signals and articulatory visualization. Another important direction concerns the representation of the speech modality itself.

8 Conclusion

SLT is effective for treating SSDs, yet access to qualified clinicians remains limited. This motivates the development of AI-driven tools to provide affordable and accessible support. In this work, we explored AAI, aiming to generate UTI directly from speech audio. We implemented an LSTM-based model that maps

40-dimensional acoustic features to 64×128 ultrasound frames, enabling clinicians to visualize tongue motion without specialized probes. To examine the role of objective functions, we compared standard pixel losses (MSE, MAE), perceptual similarity (SSIM), and hybrid formulations. Our results indicate that while LSTMs can capture some structural patterns, they fail to generalize reliably to unseen data. This highlights the intrinsic difficulty of AAI, where lower-dimensional audio must be mapped to higher-dimensional images. Despite testing multiple configurations and regularization strategies, LSTMs proved insufficient for robust generalization. These findings suggest the need for more advanced architectures. Future work should explore perceptually oriented UTI metrics, encoder–decoder designs, diffusion-based generative models, and lower-dimensional representations of UTI frames. Such methods could provide stronger multimodal alignment and more reliable articulatory reconstructions, moving AAI closer to practical use in SLT.

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